

Diversions in Forking Paths: Mapping non-linear agencies in live electronic improvisatory setups.

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Abstract

This paper presents the work of the improvisational duo *Three States of Wax*, who integrate AI-driven systems in real-time electroacoustic improvisation. Drawing on Michel Serres' re-interpretation of Descartes' wax metaphor (Serres 2012), the authors develop a live performance system in which musical material is treated as mutable, informational matter. Leveraging IRCAM's Somax2 engine (Borg, 2019), the system listens, models, and re-generates audio in evolving, non-deterministic ways. Framed within Critical Technical Practice (Agre 1997), Artificial Life (Langton 1995), and spectral theory (Derrida 1994; Fisher 2014), this work explores the co-agency of human and machine in improvisational settings. The paper details the technical design, artistic rationale, and aesthetic outcomes of this hybrid performance model.

1 Introduction

Three States of Wax (TSoW) is an experimental project developed within the Music, Thought and Technology (MTT) group at the Orpheus Institute, Ghent. The project investigates how improvisation can become a site of epistemological inquiry when extended through artificial systems.

TSoW draws conceptual inspiration from Michel Serres, particularly his reading of Descartes' wax metaphor. Rather than viewing materials as fixed objects, Serres sees them as dynamic bearers of information—shaped by their environment, history, and the processes through which they are perceived or manipulated (Serres, 1972). This philosophical stance supports our framing of sound as an informational substance that evolves through interaction with both human performers and computational agents.

The work also engages the methodological framework of Critical Technical Practice (CTP), introduced by Philip Agre (1997). CTP calls for technical work that simultaneously critiques its own assumptions. In the context of AI-augmented performance, we see improvisation not only as musical expression but as a mode of epistemic exploration—revealing how agency, memory, and authorship can be redistributed within hybrid systems.

In *Three States of Wax*, we explore improvisation as both epistemological method and live practice, foregrounding the entangled agency of humans and machines in co-creative environments. To achieve this, we have developed a distributed performance architecture using IRCAM's Somax2 engine, custom synthesis mapping, and shared vector spaces. This system facilitates nonlinear, emergent behavior across performances, enabling each performer to interact with a personalized yet responsive AI model.

We locate this system within the frameworks of CTP (Agre 1997), Alife (Langton 1995), and hauntological aesthetics (Fisher 2014), developing a speculative methodology that merges technical innovation with critical artistic research.

2 Background and Related Work

2.1 Critical Technical Practice and Improvisation

TSoW developed within MTT's ongoing engagement with *Critical Technical Practice* (CTP), a concept introduced by Philip Agre in the context of AI. He noted that researchers often present theoretical frameworks alongside technical artifacts as self-validating pairs, leaving little room for doubt, narrative, or assumption—thus denying the complexity of knowledge creation.

CTP resists the black-boxing of technical systems. Instead, it emphasizes situatedness, reflexivity, and the role of embedded assumptions in shaping technological artifacts. At the Orpheus Institute, artistic research demands that creative output not be passively accepted as knowledge. Music-making is neither the application of theory nor spontaneous expression—it is an iterative process of imagination, inscription, and reflection (Impett 2014, 2023). Improvisation serves as a methodological tool, allowing real-time probing of how systems respond, co-create, and potentially surprise.

Agre invites us to view technical practices as contingent, social, and constrained by multiple factors. MTT adopts this stance, exploring how CTP methods—such as ‘dissociation’ and ‘interference’—can help artists tell more accurate stories about their work (Impett 2021).

2.2 Spectrality, Memory, and Hauntology

TSoW treats memory and imagination as fundamentally the same kind of operation. We might understand this by analogy with Sarath's adoption of Husserlian retentive-protensive temporality (Sarath 1996) and of the future being implicit in the past. There is no creation from zero, even if things are reduced to minimal initial conditions. Such an approach is particularly resonant in the contemporary cultural dynamic polarising perpetual novelty and cyclic reinvention. Derrida's notion of *hauntology* was taken up by Mark Fisher in his critical analysis of contemporary cultures, especially in music; he refers to that repetition of that which never occurred (Fisher 2018, 172). For Fisher, it is a product of what Bifo Berardi has described as ‘the slow cancellation of the future’ (Berardi 2011, 18):

Critics were prompted to reach for the term again by a confluence of musical artists — Philip Jeck, Burial, the Ghost Box label, the Caretaker. Their work sounded “ghostly,” certainly, but the spectrality was not a mere question of atmospherics. What defined this “hauntological” confluence more than anything else was its confrontation with a cultural impasse: the failure of the future. By 2005 or so, it was becoming clear that electronic music could no longer deliver sounds that were “futuristic.” (Fisher 2012, 16)

In TSoW, sound is not treated as mere output but as a site of layered data: spectral, gestural, and historical. Each sound object carries traces of prior decisions, system responses, and embodied interaction. This echoes Derrida's concept of *hauntology*—the recurrence of that which never fully arrives but remains latent within a structure (Derrida, 1994; Fisher, 2014). The system retains fragments of past events, allowing them to re-emerge unpredictably, shaping performance memory and continuity.

2.3 Somax2 and Related Systems

Somax2 is a real-time concatenative synthesis and machine listening engine developed by IRCAM (Borg, 2019). It segments incoming audio into units, classifies them, and reassembles them based on similarity metrics. Our system extends Somax2 with real-time vector-space interaction, analog modulation, and rhythm-based control. Related systems include George Lewis's *Voyager* (Lewis 2000) and other creative AI platforms.

2.4 Previous Experiments

MTT has conducted various experiments applying CTP principles. Graph theory was explored via group improvisation: musicians acted as nodes in a dynamic system. One approach emphasized agent-based nodal behavior; another examined the edges—connections varying in influence, feedback, or decay.

George Lewis' *High Road, Low Road* (2022) extends this framework. Each performer wields instruction cards to shape their interactions, creating a network akin to a complex synthesis patch. Time, memory, and the composition-improvisation binary were explored in a re-interpretation of Frederic Rzewski's *Second Structure* (1972), which encourages progressive shifts in responsiveness—from autonomy to collective awareness. Rzewski's piece explicitly supports live electronics, adding a dimension of memory and form.

3 Some waypoints and byways

A dual view of networks, as both a society of nodes and a map of edges, constitutes a fundamental dynamic in the experimental design process and in performance. These views are both embodied in each of the two personal subsystems, the encounter of which generates the core energy of *Three States of Wax*.

3.1 Alife

Jonathan Impett's long-standing engagement with the approaches of Artificial Life is evident in the structuring of the various complement parts. A 'society' of agents perform different kinds of analysis on the performance in various configurations (individual performers and aggregate sound, instrumental and electronic elements). They look for salient features and then for resonances among their own outputs, comparing this with known features. The system then responds according to the strength of such responses: 'weak' emergence adds elements to local machine and human behaviour, while 'strong' emergence affects the whole disposition of current processes and materials. In the particular case of Impett's input, sonic, gestural and movement data are derived from the trumpet in the nth iteration of his *metatrumpet* instrument..

3.2 Timbre Networks

Timbre Networks is a creative method devised by Juan Parra Cancino, aimed to integrate a tele-communicative, algorithmic, and poetic understanding of the concept of "networks". This is done by applying dynamic mappings of control streams, which are synthesized from live and telematic musical sources, to network-based synthetic sound agents, such as stochastic synthesis and Boolean network Pattern generators (Kauffman, 1993).

The use of Timbre Networks in the context of *Three States of Wax* focused on a subset of Timbre Networks labeled *TN_chain*. This is a series of works (or rather, a single chain-shaped work) which *aims to employ each iteration/performance to inform, define and enrich the "following" iteration/performance. Our choice is to do this by preserving aspects of the performance that might be described as "highly volatile" (for example, a dancer reacting to specific elements of an*

improvisation music setting). These preserved aspects are converted into a stream of data, which is used to drive (and therefore, automatise) musical parameters of a future performance (Parra, 2019).

4. System Design and Implementation

TSoW's core experiment involves Impett (trumpet) and Parra Cancino (guitar), alongside MTT members and guests such as Brice Soniano (bass) and Ruben Martinez Orio (percussion).

4.1 Design Rationale

Each performer operates an individualized processing setup using Somax2, a real-time improvisation engine developed at IRCAM. Somax2 builds a performance buffer through continuous analysis of incoming audio, allowing it to classify and recall material based on multidimensional similarity (Borg, 2019).

To reflect aggregate system behavior, we tap Somax's internal state at both input and output. This data feeds a parallel model—slower and less reactive—forming a third voice. We also extract four normalized metrics representing melodic and harmonic matches, forming a four-dimensional vector (tesseract). Movement within this space controls an analog synthesis system, whose sustained sounds are modulated to reflect performance dynamics. Each prism face corresponds to one of 261 tesseract unfoldings, triggered by significant spatial shifts.

4.2 Implementation

- **Dual Somax2 Instances:** Each performer's engine operates autonomously but receives metadata about the other's activity. Similarity scores across four dimensions are normalized into a vector used for cross-instrument modulation and analog synthesis control.
- **Shared Vector Spaces:** Performer relations are tracked by comparing their respective vectors via the cosine of the normalized dot product:

$$\text{Cos}(\text{theta}) = \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b} / \text{abs}(\mathbf{a})\text{abs}(\mathbf{b})$$

This generates a parameter for a melodic voice, introduced intermittently.

- **Tesseract Mapping:** The vector space is mapped onto the 261 unfolded forms of a tesseract, each controlling a unique state of the analog synthesis module.
- **Rhythmic Layering:** Somax's beat-tracking is disabled to preserve rhythmic ambiguity. Instead, onset "bangs" define rhythmic units. Gaps determine fixed-length vectors that are transmitted as OSC to an external Python script, which returns related vector sequences via a k-NN model. These can be stretched, looped, or modulated within Max. Rhythmic loops vary probabilistically, and pitch is derived from long-term chroma histograms built during the performance.

5. Artistic Framing and Methodology

We situate this system as a "difference engine" that encodes both memory and transformation. Inspired by Serres, we treat sound as wax-like material: impressionable, unstable, and resistant to closure (Serres 2000). Each performance imprints and distorts traces of prior ones, forming a spectral continuum.

Improvisation here functions as speculative method and aesthetic stance. We do not seek reproducibility or linear evolution, but rather divergence, collapse, and reformation—echoing forms of organic life and memory decay (Magnusson 2019). This positions the system within the broader paradigm of performative computing: technology as participant, not tool (Born 2005; Collins and d'Esquiván 2007).

The system is designed to produce both strong and weak emergent behaviors: from subtle shifts in phrasing to wholesale changes in inter-performer dynamics. For instance, prolonged similarity between performers may collapse independent behaviors into a resonant unison, while sudden divergence can create friction or layered density.

Spectral elements from earlier sessions resurface without warning, prompting responses that feel at once familiar and uncanny—a manifestation of hauntological aesthetics.

From a performative standpoint, the system challenges conventional agency: at times it acts as a mirror, at others as a third player. The aesthetic result is not one of control but of negotiation, surprise, and shared authorship.

5.1 Form

The discourse of form in non-jazz improvised music is often hidden or ambiguous – as if improvisation were being staged, some ethos translated. But in machine-extended performance we are able to relate emergent form to present events. Again, Somax affords useful system variables with which we can shape a particular event. In particular, we have experimented with formal phenomena such as bringing the performance to focus on single pitches and clear reference to material: scheduling trajectories of continuity (from 0.0 to 1.0), transposition (incrementally reducing the list of transpositional equivalence to a precise match), sparseness (restricting output to close matches) and relative weight of influence factors (incrementally adjusting to maximise external melodic influence).

6. Conclusions

Three States of Wax embodies a hybrid artistic system that resists fixed identity. Through recursive memory, vector-based interaction, and critical theory, it offers an experimental platform where machine learning augments—not replaces—human improvisation. This work contributes to the growing field of creative AI by grounding technological design in philosophical inquiry and embodied practice. TSoW proposes a model of improvisation where human, machine, and memory interact as co-agents. It demonstrates how live performance can become a site of critical inquiry, using AI not as a tool for control but as a medium for exploration. In doing so, it bridges technical experimentation with philosophical speculation—bringing together Serres, Agre, and spectral theory into a performative laboratory of sound.

In its use of Somax-derived values, this implementation does not 'represent' the state of the Somax engines involved, any more than the project as a whole is some kind of complete manifestation or cross-medial mapping of the idea from Serres that stands at its inception. Rather, we take Serres' notion of material as something that evolves informationally with its environment, and use Somax to explore how far we might use such a principle to guide the design of a

performance system. As with any computer-extended creativity, critical reflection on the choices and decisions that machine implementation obliges us to make is as much a part of the creative process as any apparent spontaneity.

It is interesting to reflect that that the approaches and methods of digital creation and digital humanities intersect. Luciano Floridi points out that in an informational world, knowledge creation becomes constructionist (poietic) rather than descriptive (mimetic); he sees knowledge creation as the product of an iterative design process, an appropriate description of the present project (Floridi 2019, 194). In keeping with the node-edge network duality at its heart, *Three States of Wax* constitutes both an assemblage of people, practices, instruments, and technologies, and an ethos for collective, technologically extended music-making. As both research and performing environment, its approach of critical technical practice is contiguous with the constant reflection on evolving sonic material of the performing system. It is intended that current experiments with the incorporation of earlier performances will be expanded to work across the entire history of project recordings. Our various guests and irregular members thus continue to be present, participating in musical development, accumulating the history of their every interrogation and generating new responses, in the spirit of Serres' proposal.

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Appendix: Performances and scores Links

- <https://www.juanparrac.com/music/ensembles>
- <https://youtu.be/TYGA0vJHYfc?si=5Drq1CwwOMMGtbsR>
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